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Sedimentological and ichnological signatures of an offshore-transitional hyperpycnal system (Upper Miocene, Betic Cordillera, southern Spain)

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Abstract

Hyperpycnal flows have been widely described in different lacustrine and marine environments but sedimentary structures and fossil content in hyperpycnites often offer limited information about the palaeoenvironmental conditions. This limitation can be improved by ichnological analysis, which has been recently used as a tool to differentiate between different type of subaqueous deposits, even though still only a few detailed ichnological studies on hyperpycnites exist. In order to bridge this gap in knowledge, a 50 m-thick package of terrestrial organic debris-rich, dominantly structureless and well-sorted sandstone bodies alternating with burrowed siltstones (Upper Miocene, Betic Cordillera, Spain) is here analyzed. This study is based on observations of a well-exposed outcrop and cores from a well drilled just behind the outcrop to bridge field-scale observational gaps. Two type of sandbodies were typified on the basis of their stratigraphic architecture, physical sedimentary structures, and ichnofacies in the fine-grained deposits embedding them: (1) Lobate to channelized-top sandstones embebbed into silty sands with dominant highly variable degree of bioturbation by *Taenidium* and *Schaubcylindrichnus* (depauperate *Cruziana* ichnofacies) and interpreted as proximal marine sustained hyperpycnites in prodelta settings; and (2) channelized-lobate (cut-and-fill sequence) sandstones embebbed into siltstones with dominant *Nereites* and *Phycosiphon* (*Nereites* ichnofacies) interpreted as distal hyperpycnites developed in offshore settings. The studied succession is interpreted to represent the progradation of a sandy hyperpycnal system along a prodelta to starved offshore setting with high variability in grain-size, benthic food and oxygen content. Results of this study suggest that a multi-scale analysis focused on trace fossils and physical sedimentary signatures is needed to get a better understanding of these river-derived sustained-flow turbidites (hyperpycnites) that are less well known than their conventional surge-type turbidite counterparts.

Keywords: Hyperpycnite, trace fossils, core analysis, prodelta

1. Introduction

Hyperpycnal deposits (hyperpycnites) have been reported from different lacustrine and marine environments from coastal (mainly prodeltaic subenvironments), shallow-water to deep-water settings (Mulder et al., 2003; Birgenheier et al., 2017; Steel et al., 2018). Hyperpycnites contain extrabasinal (e.g., organic debris) and intrabasinal (proximal to distal marine reworked fossils) components indicating a high-efficiency transport and wide range of water depths (Mutti et al., 2007). These deposits commonly occur from prodelta subenvironments to shallow-water (above storm wave base level) siliciclastic ramps where low transport efficiency of hyperpycnal flow along low slopes is compensated by wave influence (re-suspension) during oceanic floods (Wheatcroft, 2000; Bhattacharya and MacEachern, 2009; Poyatos-Moré et al., 2016). Hyperpycnites can show components indicating a wide range of particle provenance (including terrestrial organic particles) and water depths, which challenges differentiating examples from shoreline systems (estuarine, shoreface and delta-front) from those of deep-water systems (submarine lobes) (Zavala and Pan, 2018). Physical sedimentary structures and fossil components (as most of them are reworked from proximal areas) in hyperpycnites can also offer limited information about the palaeoenvironmental conditions of the original depositional setting.

During the past decades, ichnological analysis has emerged as a powerful indicator of palaeoenvironmental evolution and associated changes, becoming a pivotal element, which supports sedimentological and stratigraphic interpretations, hence being key in sedimentary basin research (e.g., Buatois and Mángano, 2011; Knaust and Bromley, 2012). The strength of ichnological studies lays in the relationship between trace fossils and palaeoenvironmental conditions: tracemakers' behaviour records the response to biotic and abiotic factors such as salinity, oxygen, benthic food content, hydrodynamic energy, rate of sedimentation, and substrate, among others. During the last years, ichnological information has been included as a criterion to differentiate between different types of deep-water deposits such as pelagites/hemipelagites, turbidites, contourites, and hyperpycnites, yet with a variable coverage. Thus, as pelagic/hemipelagic and turbiditic sediments have been profusely studied and ichnologically well-defined (e.g., Wetzel, 2000; Uchman, 2007; Uchman and Wetzel, 2011, 2012; Wetzel and Uchman, 2012; Miguez-Salas and Rodríguez-Tovar, 2019a), contourites are now in the first phases of characterization, showing significant results (e.g., Wetzel et al., 2008; Alonso, et al., 2016; Rodríguez-Tovar and Hernández-Molina,

2018; Dorador et al., 2019; Miguez-Salas and Rodríguez-Tovar, 2019b, 2020; Miguez-Salas et al., 2019, 2020; Rodríguez-Tovar et al., 2019a,b). The ichnological characterization of hyperpycnites is also still in the first steps, with only a few studies in which trace fossils have been emphasized, showing the variability of environmental context and the absence of a unique ichnological pattern (see Buatois et al., 2019). The few existing studies on hyperpycnites documenting biogenic structures cover a wide-range of environmental settings such as lakes (Buatois and Mángano, 1993, 1998; Buatois and Mángano, 1995), deltas (MacEachern et al., 2005; Bhattacharya and MacEachern, 2009; Buatois et al., 2011; Canale et al., 2015, 2016; Dasgupta et al., 2016a,b) and deep-marine systems (Ponce et al., 2007; Wetzel, 2008; Olivero et al., 2010; Carmona and Ponce, 2011; Ponce and Carmona, 2011). There is still a lack of particular ichnological signatures, trace fossil assemblages or ichnofacies characterizing hyperpycnites, besides the variability according to their different palaeoenvironmental settings (Buatois et al., 2019). More detailed ichnological studies on hyperpycnites are therefore necessary, in order to improve the characterization of the primary and secondary processes, associated palaeoenvironmental changes, and resulting deposits.

Here we present a study of a shallow-marine succession from the Upper Miocene of the Betic Cordillera (southern Spain), based on observations of a well-exposed outcrop, and tied to a well drilled just behind the outcrop. The main aim of this study is to provide a multi-scale outcrop and subsurface integrative sedimentological and ichnological analysis to identify and to outline criteria ascribable to marine hyperpycnites (and their depositional setting), and to distinguish them from other sedimentary processes non-genetically linked to the direct connection to the river mouth.

2. Methods

The integration of outcrop observations (main observation scale in this study) and complementary subsurface data collected from a well drilled just behind the outcrop (named: Francisco Abellan well / location: 37°18'42.32 N - 3°16'30.02 W) allowed to reduce the observational gap between large- and meso- (i.e. outcrop scale) and small-scale (i.e. thin section) data.

Large- to meso-scale 2D and 3D-features of the sand-body architecture were only observable in well-exposed outcrops and described using line drawings on panoramic views. Physical sedimentary structures, large biogenic structures and sediment texture were described and represented on a stratigraphic section directly obtained from outcrop observations. This sedimentologic and ichnological study was performed by integrating outcrop observations and descriptions (stratigraphic logs and line drawing on panoramic views) with core data interpretation from a 46 m-deep well drilled behind the outcrop. Especial attention was paid on the trace fossil analysis. At outcrop scale, ichnological observations focused on macroscopic morphological features of individual burrows (i.e., shape, orientation, length and diameter) and

configuration of burrow systems, allowing to establish an ichnotaxonomical classification (Bertling et al., 2006). Moreover, variations in ichnodiversity, abundance (tentatively assigned to the Bioturbation Index (BI) of Taylor and Goldring, 1993 applied to discrete trace fossils), relationship with facies and sedimentary structures and stratigraphic distribution were analysed in detail. Outcrop limitations avoid a continuous record of the ichnological features; thus ichnological observations were mainly obtained from particular well-exposed beds. At core scale, ichnogenera characterisation was conducted based on the recognition of ichnotaxobases (Knaust, 2012, 2017), including burrow margins, sediment fill and relationship with the host rock. Extra- and intratrabasinal particles such as organic terrestrial debris, foraminifera, bioclasts and microfacies were also identified on core slabs observation and in thin sections prepared from field samples. Based on the sedimentological and ichnological features, several types of deposits were recognized and interpreted in terms of recurrent sedimentary processes and palaeological conditions. Then, stratigraphic architecture (from outcrop observation) and sedimentary-ichnological facies (from outcrop and core description) were integrated in a sedimentary-ichnological facies (SIFA) classification and interpreted in terms of proximal to distal domains of the depositional system.

3. Geological setting

The Betic Cordillera (southern Spain) represents the westernmost Alpine Mediterranean cordillera and, together with the Rif and the Gibraltar Arc System, they formed during the Early to Middle Miocene main shortening phase. Later on, from the Late Miocene onwards compressional reactivation produced tightening and lengthening of the Arc (Crespo-Blanc et al., 2016) until the modern Gibraltar Arch geography formed (Fig. 1A). During the Upper Miocene compressional reactivation stage, high-subsidence depocentres were filled by a few hundred-m thick marine successions during the Atlantic-Mediterranean connection through the Betic corridor (Martín et al., 2009; Reolid et al., 2012). One of these well-preserved and well-exposed Tortonian marine successions is found in the Guadix-Baza Basin (study area: 37.275600 lat -3.284760 long), which is located in the central part of the Betic Cordillera (southern Spain; Fig. 1A).

The Upper Miocene marine succession in the Betic Cordillera is mostly represented by two formation-rank, hectometric thick lithostratigraphic genetic units: (1) a lower siliciclastic-dominated interval (Unit I) and (2) a mixed carbonate-siliciclastic sedimentary upper interval (Unit II) (Fig. 1B,C) (Soria et al., 2003; García-García et al., 2009). Unconformably overlying these two, the next unit (Unit III) is represented by coastal deposits in transition to the thick continental succession (Units IV-VI) infilling disconnected intramountane fluvial to lacustrine basins (Viseras et al., 2005).

This study focuses on the upper part of the siliciclastic marine Unit I and the transition to the base of the mixed Unit II (Fig. 1B).

4. Results and interpretation

4.1. Stratigraphy

The 69 m-thick studied section can be divided in two parts: (1) A 62 m-thick lower part formed by a sandstone-dominated package overlying a mudstone-dominated interval and (2) a 7-m thick upper part formed by mixed carbonate-siliciclastic deposits represented by a marlstone-dominated package alternating with bioclastic sandstones) (Fig. 1D).

The siliciclastic-dominated lower part of the section consists of seven 5 to 10 m-thick bedsets each one constituted by a lower interval of coarsening-upward fine-grained deposits and an upper interval represented by a non-graded or coarsening- to fining-upward erosional sharp-based sandstone package (sandbodies 1-7) (Fig. 1D; Fig. 2A, B).

The mixed uppermost part of the section consists of a marly package with a few cm-thick mixed carbonate-sandstone beds (mixed-bed 1) (Fig. 2B - last 8.0 m in well-log depth or 62 to 69 m in stratigraphic section).

4.2. Sedimentary-ichnological analysis

Three siliciclastic and two mixed carbonate-siliciclastic lithofacies can be distinguished in the studied succession: (1) fine-grained siliciclastic deposits represented by massive siltstones and sandy siltstones, (2) medium-grained siliciclastic deposits represented by fine- to medium-grained well-sorted clean sandstones, (3) coarse- to very coarse-grained sandstones punctually containing pebble-sized mud clasts, (4) silty marls and (5) bioclastic sandstones. Trace fossil analysis reveals a low/moderate diverse trace-fossil assemblage, with significant variations in composition and abundance according to the differentiated facies (see below). Eight ichnogenera have been recognized, including *Chondrites*, *Nereites*, *Ophiomorpha*, *Phycosiphon*, *Planolites*, *Taenidium*, *Teichichnus*, and *Schaubcylindrichnus* (Fig. 2B).

Integration of lithofacies (macro- and micro-features), physical sedimentary structures, and trace fossils allowed to distinguish five sedimentary-ichnological facies (SIFA) (Fig. 2B, Table 1):

4.2.1. Massive siltstones with *Phycosiphon* (SIFA-1)

Observations. Poorly bioturbated massive siltstones (BI = 1) presents scattered < 1mm in diameter (non-Fe-oxidized) organic particles (Fig. 3A), abundant planktonic foraminifera and scarce trace fossils with a local abundance (BI = 2) of *Phycosiphon* and common *Planolites* (Fig. 3B). *Phycosiphon* is observed

in core, as patches of horizontal, curved small lobes and dark, fine grained cylindrical to circular cores encircled by lighter colored material (Fig. 3B).

Interpretation. Low bioturbated fine-grained deposits (SIFA-1) indicate slow suspension settling or fallout sedimentation under low-energy conditions at a starved offshore setting with low oxygenation or benthic food availability but eventually influenced by increase in benthic food and oxygen when short-term colonization occurs characterized by the presence of *Phycosiphon*. *Phycosiphon* is registered in fine-grained substrates from low energetic environments, being common in poorly oxygenated sediments, however the absence of a connection to the seafloor indicates oxygenated pore water in the upper sediment layer habitat (e.g., Ekdale and Mason, 1988; Wetzel and Bromley, 1994; Wetzel and Uchman, 2001; Rodríguez-Tovar et al., 2014). *Phycosiphon* is characteristic of offshore to lower shoreface, slope, and deep-marine settings, being a typical component of the *Cruziana*, *Zoophycos* and *Nereites* ichnofacies (Wetzel, 1983; MacEachern et al., 2012; Knaust, 2017).

4.2.2. Massive siltstones with *Nereites* alternating with fine-grained, organic-rich sandstones (SIFA-2)

Observations. It is represented by poorly bioturbated massive siltstones (BI = 1) with abundant planktonic and benthic foraminifera, scattered < 1 mm in diameter (non-Fe-oxidized) organic particles alternating with mm to cm-thick sharp-, erosional-based inverse to normally-graded poorly-sorted sandstones (Fig. 3C). SIFA-2 is mainly characterized by the presence (observed in core) of local abundance (BI = 2) of sub-circular burrows of *Nereites* showing an actively filled tunnel, similar in composition than the host sediment, enveloped by a halo of reworked material (Fig. 3C). Subordinately, also *Phycosiphon* is recognized appearing as, mm-wide oval or circular spots of branches and unbranched *Chondrites* and *Planolites* (Fig. 3A, B, C). *Planolites* show unlined, straight to tortuous, smooth burrows (both in core and outcrop) with structureless fill that is lithologically different from the host sediment.

Interpretation. *Nereites* is a trace fossil typical of deep-sea sediments, characteristic of the *Nereites* ichnofacies in basin-floor (flysch) deposits (Uchman, 1995; Knaust, 2017), but also occurs in the ichnofacies as the *Zoophycos* ichnofacies (MacEachern et al., 2012; Dorador and Rodríguez-Tovar, 2015). *Chondrites* is registered in a wide range of marine settings, mainly associated to fine-grained softgrounds, usually considered as an index of low-oxygen conditions (e.g., Bromley and Ekdale 1984; Savrda and Bottjer 1991). It can be interpreted as a facies-crossing trace fossil, but showing an extensive record in deep-sea (flysch) deposits assigned to *Nereites* ichnofacies (Knaust, 2017). *Planolites* is a facies-crossing form, occurring in softgrounds with fine- to medium-grained sediments from diverse environments, belonging to most of the softground marine ichnofacies but being a common component of the *Cruziana* ichnofacies (MacEachern et al., 2012; Knaust, 2017).

Low-bioturbated massive siltstones (SIFA-2) could be interpreted as the background offshore sedimentation mostly deposited by slow suspension settling or fallout sedimentation under low-energy conditions linked (1) to hypopycnal flows from suspension clouds related to delta plumes during periods of low river discharge or (2) to flow lofting at distal/off-axis marginal position of the hyperpycnal system (Zavala et al., 2011; Zavala and Arcuri, 2016). Highly bioturbated packages with *Nereites* and *Phycosiphon* assigned to the *Nereites* ichnofacies, could reveal punctual increase of benthic food and good oxygenation on the sea-floor or within the first centimeters of the substrate. Sandy packages would represent distal hyperpycnites formed by suspended sand-load at the fringing-lobe of a hyperpycnal systems where lofting processes dominate (Zavala et al., 2011). Low to local abundance of bioturbational structures and low trace fossil diversity indicate a relatively unstable setting presumably linked to the variable area influenced by hyperpycnal flows in distal prodelta to offshore transition settings as reported by Rodríguez-Tovar et al. (2014).

4.2.3. Massive sandstones (SIFA-3)

Observations. It consists of a poorly-sorted, massive fine- to medium-grained sandstones to silty sandstones with abundant (Fe-oxidized) terrestrial organic particles, and a high content in benthic-planktonic foraminifera. A low ichnodiversity and low to moderate degree of bioturbation (BI = 2-4) is represented (both in outcrop and core) by cylindrical, straight, burrows of *Taenidium* mainly subhorizontal, with a meniscate fill (Fig. 4A, C, E-F). In outcrop, subordinately, vertical stacks of horizontal to subhorizontal tubes of *Teichichnus* form straight retrusive spreiten.

Interpretation. *Taenidium* is registered in alluvial, fluvial and marginal-lacustrine environments, but also in shallow- and deep-marine deposits, being a typical component of the *Scoyenia* ichnofacies (Buatois and Mángano, 2011). However, it also occurs in other continental ichnofacies as well as marine ichnofacies as distal *Cruziana*, *Zoophycos* and *Nereites* ichnofacies (see Rodríguez-Tovar et al., 2016). *Teichichnus* occurs in a variety of environments, being typical of siliciclastic systems frequently associated to deltaic deposits (Tonkin, 2012), marginal-marine settings with lowered salinity (Knaust, 2017), and lower shoreface to offshore deposits (Pemberton et al., 2012), being a typical component of the *Cruziana* ichnofacies (MacEachern et al., 2012; Knaust, 2017).

Poorly-sorted sands (SIFA-3) are interpreted as deposited from dilute river-derived turbidity currents (hyperpycnal flows) with continental (organic particles) and marine (foraminifera) material transported in suspension. Abundant but low diverse trace fossils with *Taenidium* and *Teichichnus*, assigned to the depauperate *Cruziana* ichnofacies, point to stress conditions associated to the river floods, and associated variations in energy conditions, rate of sedimentation, substrate features and salinity in a

well-oxygenated setting (Buatois et al., 2011, 2019). These conditions are linked to energy fluctuation in a river-influenced coastal setting, close to river mouth (e.g. delta front to proximal prodelta), where proximal sustained-flow turbidity currents are common during river floods in combination with marine coastal processes (i.e. waves).

4.2.4. Intensely bioturbated mottled silty sandstones (SIFA-4)

Observations. It consists of silty sandstones with abundant Fe-oxidized terrestrial organic particles, thin-shelled bivalves. The primary sedimentary fabric is partly obliterated by high degree (BI = 3-4) of bioturbation. Ichnodiversity is moderate mainly represented by *Schaubcylindrichnus*, together with *Ophiomorpha*, *Planolites*, and *Taenidium* (Fig. 4B, D, E). *Schaubcylindrichnus* is observed in outcrop and core, as vertical to subhorizontal, single, lined tubes that are filled by sediment similar to the host rock (Fig. 4A, B). *Ophiomorpha* is registered in outcrop, as burrows with circular section, T-shaped branches, and pellets along the wall (Fig. 4D).

Interpretation. *Schaubcylindrichnus* occurs in a variety of environments from nearshore to continental slope, being common in shallow-marine settings, mainly in lower shoreface to offshore deposits (Frey and Pemberton 1991; Löwemark and Nara 2010, 2013). It is a common component of the *Cruziana* and *Skolithos* ichnofacies (Knaust, 2017). *Ophiomorpha* is registered in a variety of environments from shallow- to deep-marine, usually occurring in relatively unstable substrates, high-energy environments, thus being a significant component in the *Skolithos* and *Cruziana* ichnofacies (MacEachern et al., 2012), but it is also a component (*O. rudis*) of the *Nereites* ichnofacies (Uchman, 2009).

The abundant and moderate diverse trace fossil assemblage, with *Schaubcylindrichnus*, *Ophiomorpha*, *Planolites*, and *Taenidium*, related to the depauperate *Cruziana* ichnofacies, and primary silt-sand deposition (SIFA-4) point to relatively stressed conditions associated to fluctuating energy, rate of sedimentation and substrate instability presumably below fair-weather and above storm wave base (offshore transition). Partly oxidized terrestrial organic particles within these deposits (in contrast to non-oxidized carbon particles composing SIFA 1-2) could be linked to higher-energy currents (i.e. waves) removing the organic grains from shallower and more oxygenated settings (above storm-weather wave base) than in SIFA1-2 depositional environments.

4.2.5. Sharp-based, well-sorted clean sandstone (SIFA-5)

Observations. It is formed by sharp-based, planar or erosional-based, 1 to 5 m-thick medium- to fine-grained sandstone packages (bedsets), with a few hundred meters in lateral continuity, and showing a sheet-like to convex-up geometry (Fig. 5A, B). Sandstones are composed by detritic grains (quartz,

feldspar, rock fragments), glauconite and abundant plant debris/terrestrial organic particles, abundant benthonic and planktonic foraminifera. Trace fossils are scarce and cannot be determined (BI = 0-1). Sandstones beds forming these packages laterally onlap the erosional basal surface and they are massive or structureless in the lower part of the bedsets, and cross- to planar-stratified cm-thick inverse-to-normally graded sandstones in the middle part (Fig. 5F). They are often finer grained and display hummocky-cross stratification towards the top of the bedsets (Figs. 2B, 5C). Dewatering structures such as flame structures injecting mud into overlying sharp-based sandstones (Figs. 2B, 5D), deformed lamination such as convolute bedding, and ball-and-pillow structures are also present (Fig. 5E).

Interpretation. SIFA-5 deposits represent turbidity current deposits fed directly from rivers during sustained flood events (hyperpycnites) (Mulder and Chapron, 2011; Zavala et al., 2011). Erosional-based and convex-up top sandstone beds are interpreted to have formed on partly channelized lobes in the proximal domain of the hyperpycnal system distally evolving to more unconfined lobes in the distal domain of the hyperpycnal system (planar-based and sheet-like sandstone beds) above storm-weather wave base as indicated by combined flow reworking the top of sandstones beds. The cut-and-fill sequence (Fig. 5A, B) and transitional evolution of different tractive sedimentary structures within the sandstones indicates velocity fluctuating in sustained turbulent flows (Gamero-Díaz et al., 2011). Flame structures could be related to rapid deposition over unconsolidated sediment, or to local changes in hydraulic supercritical to subcritical flow conditions due to hydraulic jumps (Postma and Cartigny, 2014). Rapid sedimentation and high-pressure of interstitial freshwater foster penecontemporaneous dewatering and soft-sediment deformation in marine hyperpycnites. High sediment accumulation rates, determining the near absence of bioturbational structures, and high initial porosities favouring easy sediment mobilizing strongly support a hyperpycnal origin (Bhattacharya and Davies, 2001).

5. Hyperpycnite-dominated prodelta to offshore-transition depositional system

Integration of ichnological information, including ichnofacies, and other sedimentary features (e.g. texture, physical sedimentary structures), allow to interpreting variations of the sedimentary processes and of the palaeoenvironmental conditions affected by hyperpycnal flows within the studied transitional setting from prodelta to offshore setting. Ichnology helps to refine some environmental (ecological and depositional) conditions of each subenvironment (e.g., rate of sedimentation, energy conditions, oxygenation, benthic food availability, etc.).

The interpretation of thick massive to planar-laminated well-sorted clean-sandstones embedded into marine mudstones can be ambiguous (e.g., SIFA-5). Different depositional systems could fit to the above mentioned sedimentary/ichnological features, such as wave-dominated coastal sandy systems (e.g.

forced-regressive shoreface wedges), deep-water surge-type classical turbidite systems or sandy hyperpycnal systems (Zavala and Pan, 2018). Textural and physical sedimentary features are not enough for a robust interpretation of the sedimentary processes and marine environmental conditions when sand deposition occurred. The integration of a combined analysis of organic and skeletal components into sandy hyperpycnite together with trace fossil assemblages, including ichnofacies, preserved at the base and at the top of the sandy hyperpycnite should be integrated to distinguish river influence from the influence of wave and tidal currents or gravitational surge-type collapse processes. Hyperpycnal processes induce longer-time (weeks or months) changes than surge-type turbidite flows (minutes, hours) in depositional and ecological conditions (i.e., hydrodynamic energy, rate of sedimentation, grain size, salinity, nutrient availability, among others). Then, ethological response of the trace maker community to these changes, reflected in the ichnological features, could be used for the characterization and differentiation of hyperpycnites from (surge-type) turbidite flows. However, this is not an easy matter, with some research revealing the similarity between the trace fossil content of the classical turbidites and the hyperpycnites (i.e., Ponce et al., 2007; Carmona and Ponce, 2011).

In the transitional depositional setting from prodelta to offshore, previous studies have discussed the differentiation between shallow- and deep-marine depositional settings (Buatois et al., 2019 and references therein). In the case of deltaic environments, the trace maker community is mainly affected by changes in sedimentation rate, hydrodynamic energy, substrate consistency, and salinity; ichnological features of hyperpycnal flow deposits of shelf and shelf-edge deltas depositional settings reveal dominance of the depauperate *Cruziana* ichnofacies (MacEachern et al., 2005; Bhattacharya and MacEachern, 2009; Buatois et al., 2011, 2019; Canale et al., 2015, 2016; Dasgupta et al., 2016a). In deeper water settings, the main controlling factors are food supply, sedimentation rate, hydrodynamic energy, and salinity; ichnological features allow characterization of the distal *Cruziana* ichnofacies (Buatois et al., 2011) and the *Nereites* ichnofacies (*Ophiomorpha rudis* and *Nereites* ichnosubfacies) according to the particular areas of the hyperpycnal system (Buatois et al., 2019).

In this study, the registered trace fossils assemblage consisting of *Chondrites*, *Nereites*, *Ophiomorpha*, *Phycosiphon*, *Planolites*, *Taenidium*, *Teichichnus*, and *Schaubcylichnus*, show clear variations in composition, and relative abundance: a) a first group with moderate diversity and abundant bioturbation, with dominant *Schaubcylichnus*, together with *Ophiomorpha*, *Planolites*, and *Taenidium*, b) a second group with low ichnodiversity and low to abundant bioturbation with dominant *Taenidium*, together with *Teichichnus*, and c) a third group of locally abundant bioturbation, with dominant *Nereites* and *Phycosiphon*, together with *Chondrites*. According to this, the first and second

group could be assigned to the depauperate *Cruziana* ichnofacies, and the third group to the *Nereites* ichnofacies.

The first trace fossils assemblage (dominant *Schaubcylindrichnus*, together with *Ophiomorpha*, *Planolites*, and *Taenidium*) represents colonization of the wave-influenced, hyperpycnite-dominated delta front to proximal prodelta during short times of reduced sediment supply. Low ichnodiversity and low bioturbation of the second group (dominant *Taenidium*, together with *Teichichnus*) represent colonization of sand-rich hyperpycnal lobes in marginal parts of the prodelta. Thick sandy lobe-channel hyperpycnites (SIFA-5) are found embedded into finer-grained deposits containing the first and second trace fossils assemblage (SIFA 3-4) (Fig. 6). They are, therefore, interpreted as proximal hyperpycnites developed in a prodelta setting. The third trace fossils assemblage (dominant *Nereites* and *Phycosiphon*, together with *Chondrites*) represents local intense bioturbation of offshore deposits during times of hypopycnal conditions or weak influence of hyperpycnites. The complete studied succession represents the progradation of a moderate- to highly-bioturbated hyperpycnite-dominated distal delta into a previously low-bioturbated mudstone-dominated starved offshore setting. Sandy channelized-lobe hyperpycnites (SIFA-5) appear embedded into finer-grained deposits containing the third trace fossils assemblage (SIFA 1-2) (Fig. 6). They represent more distal deposits of highly-efficient in transport hyperpycnal flows at offshore settings.

Within hyperpycnal systems, radial ichnologic trends are correlated to sedimentologic trends (such axial-to-margin as proximal-distal) along the hyperpycnal systems (Buatois et al., 2011). Proximal (axial) hyperpycnal settings is represented by thickest, coarsest, erosional sharp-based SIFA-5 sandstones controlled by high sedimentation rate, high freshwater discharge and high intensity of erosion. In those proximal/axial hyperpycnal settings (prodelta), colonization window should be short (absence of bioturbation in SIFA-5) but during times of quiescence of hyperpycnal flows fostering a low ichnodiversity of low to moderate bioturbation (SIFA 3-4) represented by first and second trace fossils assemblages. Low bioturbation or absence of biogenic structures in SIFA 5 deposits suggests that these sandstones accumulated during a single sedimentation event (an hyperpycnal event). In distal (marginal) hyperpycnal settings (offshore), colonization windows should last longer favouring the trace fossil diversity represented by the third trace fossils assemblage.

The distribution of SIFA and trace fossils assemblages of the three groups (from the third to the first one) along the complete studied section represents the vertical record of the progradation (or lateral migration) of a hyperpycnite-dominated delta (delta front to prodelta subenvironment) into an offshore setting (look at the progradational stratal stacking pattern in the vertical cross-section of the diagram Figure 6).

Flame structures and asymmetric dewatering structures in SIFA-5 could be linked to a more unstable substrate, with hydraulic jumps and steeper slopes than usual in offshore settings. A tectonically-controlled irregular topography configuring a complex shallow-marine seafloor could have caused the acceleration-deceleration of hyperpycnal flows in these distal mouth-river settings and thick hyperpycnite deposition at fault-controlled, confined depocenters as documented in other tectonically active margins (Zavala et al., 2011).

6. Conclusions

At a hierarchical major-order scale, the integration of sedimentologic and ichnological data coming from two different observation-scales (outcrop with some examples from core) allowed to reconstruct the sedimentation style of part of a Tortonian succession in the Betic Cordillera (Spain). Results suggest that the studied deposits belong to a sustained sandy hyperpycnite-dominated system in the transition from a distal shallow-marine (prodelta) to offshore transition setting (below fair- and above storm-weather wave base).

At a hierarchical minor-order scale, the stratigraphic architecture analysis within the outcrop allowed to reconstruct different sub-depositional elements (channelized-lobe) at the proximal to distal segments of the hyperpycnal system. *Nereites* and *Phycosiphon*, and the associated *Nereites* ichnofacies, are linked to suspension settling from hypopycnal plumes at low-energy distal setting, with eventual deposition of distal hyperpycnal fringing lobes. *Schaubcyclindrichnus* and *Taenidium*, revealing depauperate *Cruziana* ichnofacies, are linked to channelized lobes and channels at more proximal settings of the hyperpycnal system (closer to the river mouth). These areas are more affected by stress factors controlled by fluctuating conditions in energy, rate of sedimentation, and substrate features, interaction of different marine processes (i.e., river, tidal currents, waves) and water salinity.

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Figure caption

Fig. 1A. Location of the study area at the central part of the Betic Cordillera (southern Spain). **B.** Summarized Litho- and bio-stratigraphic logs of the Neogene to Quaternary sedimentary infill of the basin (the studied interval is arrowed) (modified from García-García et al., 2009). **C.** Panoramic view of a well-exposed section showing eastward-tilted marine units (I-II) unconformably overlain by horizontal-bedded continental units (IV-VI). The studied section is located in the upper part of the first marine unit (Unit I). **D.** Studied section exposed at the cliffs on the water reservoir shoreline. Our study was focused on the sandstone-dominated package.

Fig. 2. A. Main outcrop of the studied section (see Fig. 1C for location in the panoramic view) and approximate projection of the behind outcrop well. The section is organized in different sandbodies (1-7) embedded into fine-grained deposits. The upper part of the section, with a mixed carbonate-sandstone bed (mixed-bed 1), is not visible from this viewpoint. **B.** Measured (69 m-thick) and interpretation stratigraphic section, based on fieldwork data. See text and table 1 for description of Sedimentary-Ichnological Facies (SIFA 1-5). Pictures of the figures 3-5 are located in the log.

Fig. 3. Core-scale ichno-sedimentary features of the fine-grained deposits (SIFA 1-2): **A.** Massive siltstones with scattered fine-grained organic terrestrial particles (SIFA-1). **B.** Cluster of abundant *Phycosiphon* (note the characteristic hook-shape morphology at the left ellipse) in massive siltstones (SIFA-1). **C.** *Nereites* in sandy siltstones (SIFA-2) overlain by sharp- and erosional-based fine-grained sandstones with benthic fossils (white particles) and terrestrial organic debris (black particles). **D.** Poorly-sorted fine-grained sandstones and sharp-based (dashed line) normally-graded sandstones with abundant terrestrial organic particles and abundant benthic and planktonic foraminifera (SIFA-2)

Fig. 4. A. Poorly-sorted sandstones to mottled silty sandstones (transition between SIFA 3-4) with high degree of bioturbation represented by *Schaubcylindrichnus* (see detail in **Fig. 4B**) (5 cm long scale) and *Taenidium* (see detail in **Fig. 4C**) and, **D.** Poorly-sorted mottled silty sandstones with high degree of bioturbation represented by *Schaubcylindrichnus* (SIFA-4) and *Planolites* (see *Planolites* galleries infilled

by coarser sand grains from overlying SIFA-5) (10 cm pencil for scale), **E.** Poorly-sorted mottled silty sandstones with high degree of bioturbation represented by *Schaubcylichnus* and *Taenidium* (SIFA-4 in core slab), **F.** Poorly-sorted massive sandstones with *Taenidium* (SIFA-3 in core slab).

Fig. 5. A. Panoramic outcrop view and line drawing interpretation of a sharp-erosional based and convex-up top sandstone package (SIFA-5) with more than 100 m of lateral continuity. See the internal surfaces laterally onlapping onto the erosional basal surface (oblique flow direction is towards the observer), **B.** Sharp-erosional based (white and black arrowed dashed lines) well-sorted clean sandstones (SIFA-5) overlying fine-grained deposits, **C.** Detailed view of the sharp-erosional based (white dashed line) massive and cross-bedded sandstones (SIFA-5) overlying fine-grained deposits (hammer for scale), **D.** Detail view of picture C showing flame-structures (arrows) of a mud layer projected upward into an overlying sharp-based sand bed (SIFA-5). Asymmetric mud tongues point downslope (toward the left) (5 cm long scale), **E.** Asymmetric dewatering structure in massive (or obliterated primary internal structures) sandstones potentially indicating palaeoslope dipping towards the right (5 cm long scale), **F.** Normal-to-inverse grading, planar-laminated (Sh), massive (Sm) and then again planar-laminated (Sh) subdivisions in a sandstone bed (pencil for scale). **G.** Planar-laminated (Sh) to hummocky-cross stratified (HCS) sandstone bed embedded into planktonic-rich marls (5 cm long scale)

Fig. 6. Proposed depositional model of a prograding hyperpycnal-dominated prodelta-offshore transition system, with approximate location of the studied section

Table 1. Sedimentary-Ichnological Facies (SIFA 1-5)

SIFA	Lithology	Sedimentary structures	Geometry	Trace fossils	Interpretation	Depositional environment
SIFA 1	siltstones	massive		<i>Phycosiphon (Planolites)</i> <i>Nereites</i> ichnofacies	Suspension settling	Starved offshore
SIFA 2	alternating siltstones and sands	massive, and laminated	tabular	<i>Nereites (Phycosiphon, Planolites, Chondrites)</i> <i>Nereites</i> ichnofacies	Rhythmic processes of suspension load aggradational and lofting	Distal or marginal hyperpycnal lobe at offshore
SIFA 3	sands	massive	tabular	<i>Taenidium (Teichichnus)</i> depauperate <i>Cruziana</i> ichnofacies	High-rate of gravitational collapse from sand suspension-load of sustained hyperpycnal flows	Delta front to proximal prodelta
SIFA 4	silty sands	massive	tabular	<i>Schaubcyclindrichnus</i> (<i>Ophiomorpha, Planolites, Taenidium</i>) depauperate <i>Cruziana</i> ichnofacies	Shallow-marine stable palaeological conditions with fluctuating currents energy	Wave-influenced coastal (e.g. shoreface) to shallow-water setting
SIFA 5	clean-sandstone	massive, planar- and cross-laminated	erosive-based, tabular to convex-up top	Absent or rare	High-velocity and aggradation rate of sand suspension-load from sustained hyperpycnal flows	Prodelta to offshore transition